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 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10896030>**ABSTRACT**

Introduction. Subtalar arthrodesis (SA) is currently the most appropriate method for treating isolated lesions of the subtalar joint. Although the results are usually positive, analysis and improvement of modern surgical techniques for PA help optimize treatment tactics.

Materials and methods. A search was conducted in the scientific literature for articles analyzing surgical methods for PA.

Results and discussion. The following unresolved problems have been identified: 1) early complications associated with the surgical wound in open operations, 2) insufficient tendon removal, incorrect choice of bone grafting and fixation methods, which lead to possible individual or joint nonunion; 3) conditions caused by bone graft and secondary screw removal, 4) improper or overcorrection of the heel area, possibly improper intraoperative testing of parameters, and 5) improper assessment of bony union.

As a result of the interpretation, solutions are proposed to avoid some pitfalls: 1) use of arthroscopic technique in combination with additional devices and new folds, if available, 2) use of local bone graft or allografts, if possible, 3) use of two screws for fixation for preventing rotational micromovements, 4) improving the assessment of surgical results by applying appropriate assessment of bone regeneration and adaptation.

Conclusions. The review presents practical proposals for optimizing PA methods.

Key words: subtalar arthrodesis, post-traumatic arthrosis, arthroscopy, postoperative rehabilitation period, bone union.

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СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ МЕТОДОВ ПОДТАРАННОГО АРТРОДЕЗА (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ)

АННОТАЦИЯ

Введение. Подтаранный артродез (ПА) в настоящее время является наиболее целесообразным методом лечения изолированных поражений подтаранного сустава. Хотя результаты обычно положительные, анализ и совершенствование современных хирургических методов ПА помогают оптимизировать тактику лечения.

Материалы и методы. Проведен поиск в научной литературе статей, анализирующих методы хирургического вмешательства при ПА.

Результаты и обсуждение. Выявлены следующие нерешенные проблемы: 1) ранние осложнения, связанные с операционной раной при открытых операциях, 2) недостаточное удаление сухожилия, неправильный выбор методов костной пластики и фиксации, которые приводят к возможному индивидуальному или суставному несращению; 3) состояния, вызванные удалением костного трансплантата и вторичного винта, 4) неправильная или чрезмерная коррекция области пятки, возможно, неправильное интраоперационное тестирование параметров и 5) неправильная оценка костного сращения.

В результате интерпретации предлагаются решения, позволяющие избежать некоторых ошибок: 1) использование артроскопической техники в сочетании с дополнительными приспособлениями и новыми складками, если таковые имеются, 2) использование местного костного трансплантата или аллотрансплантатов, если это возможно, 3) использование двух винты для фиксации для предотвращения ротационных микродвижений, 4) улучшение оценки хирургических результатов путем применения соответствующей оценки костной регенерации и адаптации.

Выводы. В обзоре представлены практические предложения по оптимизации методов ПА.

Ключевые слова: подтаранный артродез, посттравматический артроз, артроскопия, послеоперационный реабилитационный период, несращение кости.

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SUBTALAR ARTRODEZ USULLARINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI (ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI)

ANNOTATSIYA

Kirish. Subtalar artrodez (SA) subtalar bo'g'imning izolyatsiyalangan zararlanishlarini davolashning hozirgi vaqtdagi eng maqbul usuli hisoblanadi. Natijalar odatda ijobiy bo'lsada, SA zamonaviy jarrohlik usullarini tahlil qilish va takomillashtirish davolash taktikasini optimallashtirishga yordam beradi.

Materiallar va usullar. SA uchun jarrohlik aralashuv usullari tahlil etilgan maqolalar uchun adabiyotlarni qidiruvi o'tkazildi.

Natijalar va muhokama. Quyidagi hal etilmagan muammolar aniqlandi: 1) ochiq usulda bajarilgan operatsiyalarda jarrohlik yarasi bilan bog'liq erta asoratlar, 2) tog'ayning yetarli darajada olib

tashlanmaslik, suyak transplantatsiyasi va fiksatsiya usulini noto'g'ri tanlash, bu alohida yoki birgalikda birlashmaslikka olib kelishi mumkin; 3) suyak transplantati va ikkilamchi vintni olib tashlash natijasida yuzaga kelgan holatlar, 4) tovon sohasining noto'g'ri yoki ortiqcha tuzatilishi, ehtimol noto'g'ri intraoperativ parametrlarni tekshirish va 5) suyak birikmasini noto'g'ri baholash.

Sharhlash natijasida ba'zi xatolarni oldini olish uchun yechimlarni taqdim etadi: 1) agar mavjud bo'lsa, qo'shimcha qurilmalar va yangi burmalar bilan birgalikda artroskopik usuldan foydalanish, 2) iloji bo'lsa, mahalliy suyak transplantatidan yoki allotransplantatlardan foydalanish, 3) rotatsion mikroharakatlarini oldini olish uchun mahkamlash uchun ikkita vintni ishlatish, 4) suyak regeneratsiyasi va moslashuvini tegishli baholashni qo'llash orqali jarrohlik natijalarini baholashni yaxshilash.

Xulosa. Sharh SA usullarini optimallashtirish bo'yicha amaliy takliflarni taqdim etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: subtalar artrodez, posttravmatik artroz, artroskopiya, postoperatsion rehabilitatsiya davri, suyak o'sishishi.

Kirish

Subtalar bo'g'im murakkab bo'g'im bo'lib, oyoqning egilishida muhim rol o'ynaydi [1]. Bo'g'im yuqorida talus suyagi va pastki tomondan tog'ay suyagi o'rtasida bo'g'im hosil qiladi [2-6].

Subtalar artrodez - bu konservativ davoga mos kelmaydigan subtalar bo'g'imning izolyatsiya qilingan zararlanishlari uchun keng tarqalgan jarrohlik jarayonsi. Ko'rsatmalarga travmadan keying davr, degenerativ yoki revmatoid artrit, nerv-mushak kasalliklari, talokalkaneal birikmalar va tovon sohasi deformatsiyalari natijasida kelib chiqqan tovon sohasi kasalliklari kiradi [7-15]. Subtalar artrodezning asosiy maqsadlari og'riqni yo'qotish va tovon sohasining anatomik tuzilishini tiklashdir, bu oxir-oqibatda harakatchanlikni oshirishga olib kelishi kerak. Og'riqni yo'qotish suyak sintezi orqali amalga oshiriladi, bu bo'g'imdagi kesish kuchlarini oldini oladi va siljishni tiklash cho'qqisi bo'g'im ichidagi kuchlarni kamaytiradi.

Subtalar artrodez texnikasini ortopedik amaliyotda odatiy jarayon deb hisoblash mumkin bo'lsa-da, u ko'pincha texnik jihatdan qiyin deb ta'riflanadi [13,16-24]. Bundan tashqari, ko'plab mualliflar artrodezning birikmasligi va noto'g'ri birikishi kabi operatsiyadan keyingi jiddiy muammolar haqida xabar berishgan [8, 20, 25-29].

Tadqiqot maqsadi. Subtalar artrodezning mavjud usullarini ko'rib chiqish uchun afzallik va kamchiliklarni ko'rsating va ularni hal qilishni taklif qiling.

Usullari. Adabiyotlarni qidirish PubMed va Web of Scienceda o'tkazildi (2023 yilgacha), shuningdek, o'zaro havolalar yordamida avtomatlashtirilmagan qidiruv. Qidiruv so'zlari turli to'plamlarga birlashtirildi: subtalar bo'g'im, talokalkaneal bo'g'im, artrodez, texnika, artroskopiya, tovon sohasi deformatsiyasi, artrit va biomexanika. Rus, ingliz, nemis va golland tillaridan tashqari barcha tillarda maqolalar tanlandi. Tanlov subtalar artrodez uchun yangi texnikani taqdim etgan maqolalarni, mavjud usullarni o'zgartirishni, tez-tez uchraydigan o'zaro havolalar, sharhlar va bemorlarning katta guruhlarini (40 dan ortiq) o'z ichiga olgan tadqiqotlarni o'z ichiga olgan mavhum qidiruvga asoslangan edi.

Odatda, jarrohlik amaliyoti qo'shilishdan xaftaga va subxondral suyak qatlamlarini olib tashlashni o'z ichiga oladi. Keyinchalik, oshiq va tovon suyaklarining qon ketish yuzalari tekislanadi va kerak bo'lganda o'rnatiladi. Oxir-oqibat, yuzalar birlashib, subtalar bo'g'ini harakatsiz holga keltiradi. Ushbu umumiy protokoldan so'ng, subtalar artrodez jarayonini beshta alohida bosqichga bo'lish orqali tuzilgan tahlil o'tkazildi. Har bir qadam uchun adabiyotda tavsiflangan turli xil variantlar, ularning afzalliklari va kamchiliklari va adabiyotda taqdim etilgan potentsial yechimlar bilan birga umumlashtiriladi.

Statistik tahlil qilish imkoni yo'q edi, chunki ob'ektiv ma'lumotlar kam edi. Shuning uchun, kamchiliklarni va cheklovlarni aniqlashda yordam berish uchun turli og'irlikdagi muvaffaqiyat darajasi va asoratlar darajasi hisoblab chiqilgan. Qisqa kuzatuv davriga ega bo'lgan 10 dan kam bemorning natijalarini bildiruvchi tadqiqotlar noto'g'rilikni kamaytirish uchun chiqarib tashlandi (10 ta maqola). Anatomik korreksiya qilishni talab qiladigan tovon sohasi deformatsiyasi bo'lgan

bemorlarning populyatsiyasi bir guruhga birlashtirildi [9,12,16-21,26,29-36]; boshqa ko'rsatkichlari bo'lgan maqolalar ikkinchi guruhga birlashtirildi [8,11,13,15,22-25,27,28,37-64].

Yuqoridagi 50 ta tadqiqotning klinik natijalarini umumlashtirish uchun har bir guruh uchun vazni muvaffaqiyat darajasi hisoblab chiqilgan. Bu tadqiqotda batafsil bayon qilingan yaxshi va mukammal klinik natijalar foiziga ko'paytiriladigan og'irlik faktorini yig'ishdan iborat edi. Har bir tadqiqot uchun og'irlik koeffitsienti ushbu tadqiqotda operatsiya qilingan subtalar bo'g'inlar sonining klinik natijalarni shunga o'xshash tarzda hisobot bergan boshqa barcha tadqiqotlarda operatsiya qilingan subtalar bo'g'imlarning umumiy soniga bo'lish sifatida aniqlandi. Shunday qilib, bemorlarning kattaroq populyatsiyalari natijalarini hisobot qiladigan tadqiqotlar, kichikroq bemorlar populyatsiyasi haqida xabar berilgan maqolalarga qaraganda, og'irlikdagi ballning yuqori ulushiga ega. Xuddi shunday hisob-kitob og'irlikdagi asoratlarning darajasi uchun ham amalga oshirildi. Yara infeksiyasining asoratlari, neyrovaskulyar tuzilmalarning shikastlanishi va jarohatni davolashning kechkii alohida guruhlarga ajratilmagan. Og'irlangan klinik natija yoki asoratlarni hisoblash uchun foydalanilgan barcha ma'lumotnomalar, shuningdek, hisoblash uchun foydalanilgan bajarilgan operatsiyalarning umumiy soni.

Tadqiqot natijalari.

Jarrohlik yondashuvi

Jarrohlik yondashuvi bemorning pozitsiyasiga va jarrohlik usulga bo'linadi. Umumiy ochiq usullar uchun bemorlar yonbosh holatiga, zararlanmagan tomonga tomonga yotqiziladi [13,22,24,27,28,33] yoki ko'tarilgan holda yotqiziladi [13,22,24,27, 28,33]. Subtalar bo'g'imiga kirish odatda (63 ta tadqiqotning 68%) lateral yondoshuv orqali amalga oshiriladi, bunda yoki oshiq sinusi ustidagi qiya kesma yoki fibulaning uchidan pastki qismigacha kesma amalga oshiriladi. 4-metatarsal suyak yoki uzunlamasina L kesmasi qo'yiladi [8-10, 12,15,17,19-23,25-29,31-35].

Oyoq o'lchami bilan solishtirganda, ochiq usullarda yara infeksiyasi xavfi mavjud bo'lgan nisbatan katta kesmalar qo'llaniladi (1089 holatdan 5%, diapazon 1-45%) [8,13,15,21,23, 26-28,31], neyrovaskulyar shikastlanish (umumiy hisobda 10% 426 fut, diapazon 3-33%) [8,22,27] va kechiktirilgan jarohatni davolash (umumiy hisobda 262 ta holatda 2,5%, 1-5% oraligi) [29, 33]. Ushbu erta asoratlarning oldini olish uchun artroskopik yondashuvdan foydalanish mumkin, chunki xavfsiz kirish portlarini ishlab chiqish bo'yicha harakatlar olib borilmoqda va klinik tadqiqotlar hech qanday infeksiya yoki neyrovaskulyar shikastlanishni ko'rsatmaydi [24]. Shu bilan birga, artroskopiyaga qarshi ko'rsatmalar tovon sohasining jiddiy siljishi va talus yoki tovon suyagining sezilarli darajada siljishini o'z ichiga oladi [24]. Bundan tashqari, artroskopik usullar jarrohlik aralashuvi nuqtai nazaridan ko'proq mahorat talab qiladi [24, 32]. Ko'pgina tadqiqotlar subtalar artrodezga artroskopik yondashuvlarni taqdim etganligi sababli, natijalar haqida xabar berilganligi sababli, qisqa muddatli kuzatuvga ega bo'lgan 10 dan kam bemor og'irlikdagi muvaffaqiyat yoki asoratlarni hisoblashdan chiqarildi.

Tog'ayni olib tashlash

Subtalar bo'g'imning qon ketishi bilan aloqa yuzalarini yaratish yetarli o'sishishga erishishning asosiy bosqichidir. Tegishli yuzalarni saqlab qolish uchun barcha xaftaga va taxminan 2 mm subkondral suyakni olib tashlash kerak. Ochiq usullardan foydalanib, barcha qirralar ham chisel va osteotom [8] bilan chiqariladi. Orqa fasetni olib tashlash artroskopik usullarda küretkalar va burrs yordamida amalga oshiriladi [21,31].

Ushbu jarrohlik bosqichining nochorligi xaftaga va subkondral suyakning etarli darajada olib tashlanmaganligidir. To'liq olib tashlashni osonlashtirish uchun yumshoq to'qimalarni [9,12,17,20,21], plastinka tarqatuvchilarni [15, 27], chalg'ituvchi asboblarni [13, 22] yoki to'mtoq troakarlarni [23, 32] olib tashlash orqali qo'shimcha ish joyi yaratilishi mumkin. Endi invaziv bo'lmaganlar mavjud intraoperativ qo'shma bo'shliqni oshirish uchun chalg'ituvchi vositalar [81]. To'qimalarni to'liq olib tashlash, shuningdek, artroskopik yondashuv yordamida qo'shma vizualizatsiyani yaxshilash orqali ham osonlashtiriladi [51,54].

Suyak transplantatsiyasi

Suyak transplantatlari suyak nuqsonlari mavjud bo'lganda yoki tekislashni korreksiya qilishni talab qiladigan bemorlarda qo'llaniladi. Biroq, suyak transplantatlaridan foydalanish har doim ham

talab qilinmaydi [33]; ular o'sishish darajasini oshiradi [28]. Uch turdagi transplantatlar qo'llanilgan: kortikal, kantsellöz va estrodiol kortiko-kanselli transplantatlar. Kansellus suyak transplantatlari asosan takozlarni to'ldirish uchun ishlatiladi va shu bilan suyakning kontakt yuzasiga nisbatini oshiradi [8, 13, 22, 25]. Kortikal transplantatlar tovon sohasi deformatsiyasini korreksiya qilish uchun mos keladigan kuchli va qattiq tayanchni ta'minlaydi [13, 16, 18, 22, 27]. Kamchilik, suyak transplantatlari bilan solishtirganda birlashish uchun uzoq vaqt va birlashmaslik ehtimoli biroz yuqori bo'lishi mumkin [13, 16, 22].

Shunday qilib, ko'plab mualliflar [9, 12, 15, 19-21] tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanganidek, kortiko-kanselli suyak transplantatlari yaxshi alternativ hisoblanadi. Avtotransplantatlar yonbosh suyagidan [8, 13, 15] yoki tibia yoki fibuladan [8, 9, 12, 16, 18] olinadi.

Ular qo'shimcha jarrohlik amaliyotini talab qiladi, bu esa bemorlarning jarrohlik kasallanishini oshirishi mumkin. Bunga yo'l qo'ymaslik uchun transplantatlarni to'g'ridan-to'g'ri tog'ay suyagidan to'plash mumkin [8, 15, 23, 28]. Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, allotransplantatlar natijalari ishonchli emas [8, 17]. So'nggi tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, strukturaviy allotransplantatlar rekonstruktiv muolajalar uchun mos keladi [34, 36]. Nihoyat, suyak birikmasini yaxshilash uchun yangi va istiqbolli usullar, masalan, tashqi elektr stimulyatsiyasi yoki birlashmaslik xavfi yuqori bo'lgan bemorlarda past intensivlikdagi ultratovush tekshiruvi, ammo aniq klinik dalillarni taqdim etish uchun qo'shimcha tadqiqotlar talab etiladi [23, 27].

Tovon sohasi deformatsiyasini korreksiya qilish

Jarrohlik paytida oyoqning anatomik holatini qo'lda tekislash, shuningdek, medial yoki lateral tomondan ortiqcha suyakni olib tashlash usullari tasvirlangan. Subtalar bo'g'imi [21,27,28] va suyak transplantatini ochiq xanjarsimon usulda joylashtirish mumkin [13,15,32,34]. Tovon sohasini korreksiya qilishning mashhur usuli bu suyak bloke bilan distraksiya qilish usuli bo'lib, oyoq osti bo'g'imining lateral tomoniga suyak blokini qo'yish orqali tovon sohasi valgusini korreksiya qilishdir [8,9,12,17,19,20,22,26-29].

Funksional natija uchun aniq korreksiya qilish muhim ahamiyatga ega [30]. Ushbu maqsadga erishish uchun bir nechta vositalar qo'llaniladi: operatsiyadan oldin va operatsiyadan keyingi og'irlikdagi lateral to'piq rentgenogrammasida bir tomonlama yoki ikki tomonlama baholash va operatsiyadan oldin va keyin tovon sohasining tekislanishini baholash va goniometrlar yordamida operatsiya qilish [11, 33]. Shu bilan bir qatorda, ba'zi mualliflar oshiq va tovon suyaklari o'rnini o'zgartirganda va suyak transplantati ochiq xanjarga sig'dirish uchun kesilganda paydo bo'lgan ochiq burchakni o'lchagan [8,27,35,36,43,59,64]. Yaqinda intraoperativ korreksiya qilish miqdorini o'lchash uchun floroskopiya joriy etildi [28,34].

Tovon sohasi deformatsiyasini korreksiya qilishni talab qiladigan bemorlar uchun klinik natijalar odatda boshqa ko'rsatkichlarga qaraganda kamroq qulaydir (1001 ta holatdan 65% og'irlik darajasi, 36-96% diapazon) [9,12,16-21,26] holatlar, diapazon 68-100% [8,11,15,23,24]. Qoniqarli tovon sohasi hizalanishiga erishish uchun cheklovlar juda tez-tez qayd etilgan [18,23,25,26,30]. Buni haddan tashqari to'g'rilash yoki noto'g'ri korreksiya qilish tufayli nisbatan yuqori asorat darajasi tasdiqlaydi: faqat tovon sohasi deformatsiyasi bo'lgan tadqiqotlar uchun 883 holatdan 24% ni tashkil qiladi (diapazon 2-51%) [9,12,16-19,26,29- 32,34,36] boshqa ko'rsatkichlarga ega bo'lgan tadqiqotlar uchun 421 holatdan 5% og'irlik darajasi bilan solishtirganda (diapazon 3-9%) [8,22,37]. Bu raqamlar faqat ko'rsatkichdir, chunki artrodezdan keyin tovon sohasining tiklanishini aniqlash usullari juda xilma-xildir [26].

Fiksatsiya turlari

Artrodezning mustahkam birlashishiga erishish uchun suyak yuzalarining dastlabki mustahkam aloqasi muhim ahamiyatga ega. Fiksatsiya qilishning uchta usuli tavsiflangan: tog'ay suyagi bo'ynidan tog'ay suyagiga o'rnatilgan vint yordamida oldingi yondashuv [31, 32], tog'ay suyagi tuberkulyozidan talusga o'rnatilgan vint yordamida orqa yondashuv [8,27] va plantar yondashuv [20,27]. Odatda, siqish talar va kalkaneal qo'shma yuzalarning markazi orqali joylashtirilgan bir yoki ikkita kanulli vintlar yordamida amalga oshiriladi. Muqobil variant - shtapel bilan mahkamlash [11,23]. Vintning to'g'ri o'rnini tekshirish uchun turli usullar qo'llaniladi: xochsimon bog'lamli yo'naltiruvchi matkaplar [22, 33], floroskopiya [8, 25, 27], hidoyat pinlari [24,25] va floroskopiya va

yo'naltiruvchi simlarning kombinatsiyasi [13, 15, 24]. Ba'zi artroskopik usullar to'g'ridan-to'g'ri artroskopik rahbarlik ostida vintlarni joylashtirishni tekshirishi mumkin [31].

Noto'g'ri fiksatsiyaga olib keladi : tovon sohasining eksklyuziv deformatsiyasi (diapazon 2-46%) bo'lgan tadqiqotlar uchun 953 ta holatda 14% masofada og'irlik darajasi [12, 17-21, 26, 30-32] boshqa ko'rsatkichlarga ega bo'lgan tadqiqotlar uchun 864 holat chuqurligida 10% og'irlikdagi nisbati (diapazon 2-30%) [8, 15, 22, 25, 27].

Umumiy jihatlar

Jarrohlik usullaridan tashqari, bemorning ahvoli va operatsiyadan keyingi parvarish ham funktsional natijaga ta'sir qiladi. Semizlik, diabet, revmatoid artrit va og'ir nerv-mushak kasalliklari natijaga [8], shuningdek, tovon sohasi deformatsiyasining og'irligiga va tog'aylarni ko'chirish zarurligiga sezilarli darajada salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi [28].

Umuman olganda, olti haftalik vaznga ega bo'lmagan gips tavsiya etiladi, so'ngra bir necha hafta davomida olti haftalik vaznli gips tavsiya etiladi. Ilgari, erta yuklash (ya'ni, olti haftadan oldin) subtalar artrodezning muvaffaqiyatsizligiga olib keldi [18,31]. So'nggi paytlarda operatsiyadan keyingi istalgan vaqtda to'liq yuk ko'tarish kam sonli asoratlar va yuqori birlashish tezligi bilan qayta tiklandi [24,28-31].

Natijalarni muhokama qilish. Ushbu adabiyotni ko'rib chiqish orqali biz subtalar artrodez texnikasining beshta operativ bosqichining har biri uchun variantlarni, afzalliklarni va kamchiliklarni va mavjud yechimlarni aniqladik. Mavjud adabiyotlarni taqqoslash ko'rsatkichlarning xilma-xilligi, shuningdek, demografik va bemorlar populyatsiyasi tufayli qiyin bo'ldi. Ma'lumotlarni birlashtirish orqali statistik tahlilni o'z ichiga olgan meta-tahlil mumkin emas edi, chunki nashr etilgan seriyalar har doim tovon sohasi patologiyalarining kichik, geterogen guruhlari bo'yicha retrospektiv sharhlar edi [15]. Bundan tashqari, cheklov shundan iboratki, yaqinda operativ usullar va baholash protokollari aniq talqin va baholash imkonini beradigan darajada batafsil tavsiflanmagan [13,15,29]. Shuni esda tutish joizki, ushbu tadqiqotda hisoblangan vaznli natijalar faqat ko'rsatkichdir va statistik ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan ma'lumotlarni taqdim eta olmaydi.

Subtalar artrodez usullarining quyidagi afzalliklari va kamchiliklarini ta'kidlash mumkin:

- jarrohlik travmatikligi bilan bog'liq erta asoratlar;
- tog'ayning yetarli darajada olib tashlanmaganligi, suyak transplantatini va fiksatsiya usulini noto'g'ri tanlash, buning natijasida birlashmaslik kuzatilishi mumkin;
- suyak transplantatini va vintni olib tashlash tufayli qo'shimcha travmatizatsiya;
- intraoperativ tekshirish tufayli tovon sohasining joylashishini noto'g'ri korreksiya qilish yoki ortiqcha korreksiya qilish;
- suyak o'sishishini noto'g'ri baholash.

Artroskopik usulni yangi freza atributlari, mahalliy suyak transplantati yoki allotransplantat yordamida, rotatsion mikroharakatlarni oldini olish va jarrohlik natijalarini baholashni yaxshilash uchun fiksatsiya uchun ikkita vintni ishlatib, tegishli diagnostika vositalari, batafsil o'lchovlar va tasdiqlangan natijalar o'lchovlari protokollari bilan birgalikda qo'llash maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi. Suyak sintezining qattiqligi haqida shubha tug'ilsa, kompyuter tomografiyasi tavsiya etiladi, bu esa o'sishish kuch darajasini aniqlash imkonini beradi. Agar subtalar qo'shma yuzalarning 50% dan ortig'i birlashtirilgan bo'lsa, kelajakda subtalar artrodez uchun operativ texnikaga taklif qilingan ko'plab korreksiya qilishlarning ta'sirini baholash uchun uzoq muddatli kuzatuv tadqiqotlarini o'tkazishga harakat qilish mumkin.

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